

OZONE IN CZECH REPUBLIC

State, Trends and Projections

This factsheet provides an in-depth analysis of ground-level ozone in Czech Republic. It presents long-term trends in ozone concentrations (2005-2023), changes in precursor emissions (CH₄, NMVOCs and NO_x) over the same period, transboundary contributions at the national level in 2023, and an example of sector apportionment at one station in 2024 for daily maximum 8-hour average (MDA8) ozone concentrations. It also provides projections of ozone levels in 2050 under various emission scenarios. This analysis is based on multiple datasets, including both observations (data from EEA database) and modelling data (from chemistry transport models like CHIMERE and EMEP/MSC-W).

1. LONG-TERM TRENDS

Analysis of long-term ozone trends based on monitoring stations (Gbangou and Colette, 2023¹) is presented for different station typologies. The analysis includes the annual mean ozone concentrations, the ozone peak (percentile 99 of ozone MDA8) concentrations and the peak-season (average MDA8 from April to September). Relative changes (in %) between 2005 and 2023 are calculated for each station typology. The trends are derived from validated monitoring data from the EEA AirBase and the Verified Data (E1a) databases and describe the evolution of ozone levels over the period 2005-2023. Regional trends within the country may diverge from this national average analysis.

Between 2005 and 2023, for Czech Republic: the annual average mean ozone concentration showed a **10.0% increase**, the peak season (April–September) average showed a **1.7% increase**, and the averaged ozone peak concentration (4th highest MDA8) showed a **7.3% decrease** compared to 2005.

2. PRECURSOR EMISSIONS

Historical trends of NO_x, NMVOC, and CH₄ emissions for 2005-2023 are presented along with the relative change and the share of the country emissions. Data are based on the National Emission reduction Commitment Directive (EU)

2026/2284 for NO_x and NMVOC. Member States are required to annually report on their national CH₄ emissions, as part of their GHG emission inventories under the Energy Governance Regulation*. Emission data were extracted in June 2025; later submissions were not considered in this analysis.

Czech Republic has achieved reductions in ozone precursor emissions between 2005 and 2023. **NMVOC emissions decreased by 34.4%, NO_x emissions decreased by 53.1%, CH₄ emissions decreased by 23.5%.**

Regarding Czech Republic's contribution to total EU27 emissions: **NMVOC: 4.0%** in 2023; **NO_x: 2.7%** in 2023; **CH₄: 2.9%** in 2023.

* CH₄ data were extracted from the [EEA greenhouse gases — data viewer](#), and amended to express the correct unit, as CH₄ data were reported as t CO₂ eq, which requires dividing the data by 28 (GWP of CH₄ according to the 5th IPCC Assessment Report) and by 1000 (to change from t to kt).

3. SECTOR APPORTIONMENT & TRANSBOUNDARY CONTRIBUTIONS

Sector apportionment

Source apportionment analysis is based on CHIMERE Air Control Toolbox estimations under the CAMS Policy Support Service (<https://policy.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/yearly/>). This analysis quantifies sectoral contributions to ozone formation from Natural and Hemispheric, Agriculture, Industry, Residential, Road transport (traffic), international and national Shipping as well as other sources. The other sources include solvents, aviation, offroad, waste and the

GNFR sectors others. Stacked bar charts illustrate the contributions of different emission sources to MDA8 ozone concentrations. Both the peak season (ozone MDA8 April-September average) and peak episodes (99th percentile) are presented **for the station with the highest number of days exceeding the Target Value threshold for the protection of human health in 2024, which geographical location can be seen in the map.** In the peak concentration graph, the Long-Term Objective (LTO) of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ established in the revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive (2024/2881) is displayed as a red dashed line. The visualisation suggests that targeted reductions in anthropogenic emissions - particularly from traffic, industry, residential heating, and agriculture - could bring ozone levels closer to or even below this regulatory threshold. In addition, emission reductions from the shipping sector could provide additional mitigation potential, especially in coastal areas and countries with significant maritime activity.

At this station, on average, for ozone peak concentrations, **Traffic (31.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), Industry (23.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and Others (solvents, aviation, offroad, waste and the GNFR sector “others”) (11.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)** are the main anthropogenic contributors.

Transboundary contributions

Analysis of transboundary pollution contributions is presented for Czech Republic. The analysis is based on source-receptor matrices that quantifies transboundary air pollution by estimating how emissions from one country affect air quality in other countries. The matrices behind the graphs are calculated using the EMEP MSC-W model (version rv5.6) for meteorological and chemical conditions of 2023, covering the EMEP domain (30°N-82°N, 30°W-90°E) at 0.3° × 0.2° longitude-latitude resolution driven by ECMWF-IFS meteorology (EMEP Status Report 1/2025²). The methodology employs a 15% perturbation approach, whereby emissions of NO_x and NMVOC are reduced by 15% separately for each emitter country, with no extrapolation to larger reductions and no simultaneous perturbations in neighbouring countries. The resulting changes in air concentrations in receptor countries are computed. For ozone indicators (for instance MDA8), the effects of NO_x and NMVOC emission reductions are reported separately, as ozone formation responds differently to these precursors depending on local chemical regimes. It should be noted that in the bar charts, the sum of the absolute values of these effects corresponds to 100%. The percentage values give the importance of the various emitter countries that influence concentration in Czech Republic (positive or negative). Reductions are represented by positive values. Hence, a negative bar in the chart means that a reduction in emissions from an emitter country would lead to an increase in concentration in Czech Republic. In some countries, this can occur because of non-linearities in chemistry. Contributions from areas outside the EMEP domain are not included in the ozone tables, since the dominant external contribution comes from hemispheric background ozone transport rather than from precursor emissions at the model boundaries. In addition to the countries included in the EU-27, regions such as the Northeast Atlantic Ocean (ATL), the North Sea (NOS), the Baltic Sea (BAS), the Black Sea (BLS), the Caspian Sea (CAS), the Mediterranean Sea (MED), and North Africa (NOA) are considered emitting regions. The following graphs illustrate the relative contributions of different countries and

regions to MDA8 ozone concentrations, based on the source-receptor relationships for NO_x and NMVOC emissions.

Regarding transboundary contributions, **21.2%** of NMVOC-related ozone formation originates from national sources, while **78.8%** comes from transboundary transport. For NO_x, **24.0%** originates from national sources and **76.0%** from transboundary sources. The main contributing countries for NMVOC are **Germany, Poland, France**. The main contributing countries for NO_x are **Germany, Poland, France**.

Chemical regime at SPOs with exceedance of the Target Value threshold for protection of human health

A chemical regime analysis was performed at up to three background monitoring stations (SPO) per country — representative of urban, suburban and rural environments — selected as those recording the highest number of days with MDA8 ozone concentrations exceeding the EU Target Value for human health protection (120 µg/m³). The graphs, based on the Air Control Toolbox surrogate model (Real et al., 2024³), show how ozone concentrations respond to reductions in industrial (IND) and road transport (TRA) emissions. Each point on the chart represents a combination of emissions reductions (0-100%) applied to both sectors simultaneously. Blue areas indicate that emission reductions effectively decrease ozone concentrations. Red areas indicate the opposite: reducing emissions paradoxically increases ozone (titration effect). The dashed black line marks boundary between these two regimes. The slope of the isopleths reveals which sector drives ozone the most: steeper vertical gradients indicate sensitivity to TRA reductions, while steeper horizontal gradients indicate sensitivity to IND reductions. As shown by Real et al. (2024) for 22 European cities, most locations — especially in southern Europe during summer — are either TRA-sensitive or equally sensitive to both sectors, while titration regimes dominate in winter and in northern European cities with low solar radiation.

O₃ SPOs - Czechia (2024) Days exceeding 120 µg/m³

SPO #1 (CZ_ZZZSA) – Urban Background
Czechia – Peak season 2024
O₃max (%): Scénario – REF

SPO #2 (CZ_HKRYA) – Rural Background
Czechia – Peak season 2024
O₃max (%): Scénario – REF

SPO #3 (CZ_UTPMA) – Suburban Background
Czechia – Peak season 2024
O₃max (%): Scénario – REF

4. PROJECTIONS

Future ozone projections are presented under three different emission scenarios. The CLE (current legislation) scenario assumes full implementation and enforcement of all adopted energy and environmental policies. The MFR (maximum feasible reductions) mitigation scenario assumes complete deployment of proven technical mitigation measures for precursor emissions, as included in the GAINS model. The LOW mitigation scenario extends the MFR by incorporating additional policies targeting transformations in the agricultural sector. All emission projections are consistent with the EU third Clean Air Outlook (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/air/clean-air-outlook_en) and are based on EMEP/MSC-W atmospheric chemistry transport model simulations. Results (based on van Caspel et al., 2024⁴) demonstrates the potential for ozone reductions through combined NO_x, NMVOCs and CH₄ emission control.

Global emission totals for the CLE, MFR and LOW emissions scenarios in Tg yr¹ for 2015, 2030 and 2050. Emission totals within the EMEP region, which includes the member countries of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) region excluding North America and Israel, are listed in brackets (W. E. van Caspel et al., 2024)

Species	Scenario	2015	2030	2050
NO _x	CLE	119 (16)	103 (10)	106 (9)
	MFR		65 (6)	38 (4)
	LOW		62 (6)	25 (3)
NMVOCs	CLE	121 (15)	118 (14)	121 (14)
	MFR		68 (10)	59 (8)
	LOW		63 (9)	48 (8)
CO	CLE	517 (50)	427 (37)	405 (43)
	MFR		160 (22)	123 (18)
	LOW		149 (22)	91 (17)
CH ₄	CLE	334 (62)	371 (60)	428 (60)
	MFR		229 (28)	210 (22)
	LOW		219 (27)	168 (14)

Based on EMEP model simulations, Czech Republic shows a 2015 baseline population-weighted peak season MDA8 concentration of **96.7 µg/m³**. By 2050, projections indicate: under the **Current Legislation (CLE)** scenario: **86.9 µg/m³** (-10.1%); under **Maximum Feasible Reduction (MFR)**: **75.5 µg/m³** (-21.9%); under the **LOW** scenario: **71.4 µg/m³** (-26.2%). Even under the most ambitious scenario (MFR), concentrations would remain **15.5 µg/m³** above the WHO guideline of 60 µg/m³, highlighting the need for additional measures.

¹ Gbangou, T. and Colette, A. (2023). *Long-term trends of air pollutants at European and national level 2005-2021* (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2023/8). European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment.

² EMEP Status Report 1/2025. *Transboundary particulate matter, photo-oxidants, acidifying and eutrophying components* Joint MSC-W & CCC & CEIP & CIAM Report.

³ Real, E., Megaritis, A., Colette, A., Valastro, G., and Messina, P. (2024). *Atlas of ozone chemical regimes in Europe*, Atmos. Env., 320, ISSN 1352-2310, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2023.120323>.

⁴ van Caspel, W. E., Klimont, Z., Heyes, C., and Fagerli, H. (2024). *Impact of methane and other precursor emission reductions on surface ozone in Europe: scenario analysis using the European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP) Meteorological Synthesizing Centre – West (MSC-W) model*, Atmos. Chem. Phys., 24, 11545-11563, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-24-11545-2024>.

